

THE USAGE OF INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING ENGLISH

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Abstract. The article presents the usage of information and communication technologies in teaching foreign language. Also, the article deals with the essence of information and communication technologies, their role in teaching foreign language in conditions of modernization of education, a classification of using for new information technologies in teaching foreign language. The conclusion is made about the expediency of using ICT to improve the quality of students' knowledge, to increase the interest for the lessons

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In the modern world, education plays an important role in the society. Moreover, the requirements for the education system and for the knowledge of student have changed. Based on the realities of today's life, the skills of schoolchild of the 21st century are identified: high professionalism in a certain area, the ability to present and present oneself, knowledge of psychology, the ability to apply knowledge in the condition of real life. Such competencies in the education system are developed through the use of innovative pedagogical technologies.

Information and communication technologies (ICT) can be distinguished among all educational technologies. We believe that the use of ICT in educational activities contributes to the achievement of meta-subject educational outcomes. In the Standard, meta-subject educational outcomes are defined as "mastered interdisciplinary concepts of students and universal educational actions (regulatory, cognitive, communicative), the ability to use them

in educational, cognitive and social practice, independence of planning and implementation educational activities and the organization of educational cooperation with teachers and peers, building an individual educational trajectory”³⁶.

The use of multimedia in English lessons helps to implement of personality-oriented approach to learning, provides individualization and differentiation, taking into account the characteristics of children, their interests and inclinations.

However, the prospects for the usage of “information and communication technologies in the educational activities of the school depend on the pedagogical factors, these are, on the level of the teacher’s ICT competence, his/her general erudition, his/her readiness and ability to integrate ICT into educational activities”³⁷. Therefore, a modern teacher needs to improve constantly the level of

professional qualifications, follow all the innovations in the field of education, attend seminars, conferences, master classes and round tables. One of the forms of increasing the teacher’s ICT competence can be participation in the creative laboratory.

The use of ICT in the study of foreign languages promotes:

- development of creative possibilities and abilities of students;
- creating conditions for self-education of students in the areas of interest to them;
- increasing the level of using visibility in the lesson;
- improving the productivity of the lesson;
- establishment of interdisciplinary connections;
- the acquisition of real experience of intercultural education;
- enriching students’ knowledge about history and culture of other countries of the target language;
- developing the ability to navigate in modern foreign language environment.

In a modern system education, a situation has developed when the well-established methods, techniques and forms of teaching require reflection, correction and new

³⁶ Farhodov A.G. Today ICT plays essential role. Tashkent, 2018, 28p

³⁷ Koptyug N. M. Internet lessons as auxiliary material for an English teacher // Foreign languages at school. - 2000. - № 4.

pedagogical solutions. This is primarily due to the widespread introduction and widespread usage of information and communication technologies. Similar technologies are actively used to transfer information and ensuring interaction. The usage of new information technologies in teaching is one of the most important aspects of improving and optimizing educational process, enrichment of the arsenal of methodological tools and techniques that allow you to diversify the forms of work and make the process of teaching a foreign language

interesting and memorable for students.

In modern science, there are many different approaches to the definition of the term “information and communication technologies”. According to the dictionary pedagogical use (under the editorship of L.M. Luzina), information and communication technology is a set of tools and methods for transforming information data to obtain information of a new quality (information product).

In modern sources, information and communication technologies represent a wide range of digital technologies used for the creation, transmission and distribution of information and the provision of services (computer equipment, software, cellular, electronic mail, cellular and satellite technologies, wireless and cable networks, multimedia, and the Internet).

According to G.K Selevko, “pedagogical (educational) technology is a functional system of all components of the pedagogical process, is built on a scientific basis, programmed on time and space, leading are intended to results”. By methods and ways of teaching and upbringing, he distinguishes the following pedagogical technologies: dogmatic, reproductive, explanatory and illustrative, coercion, free choice, programmed education, problematic, search, research, developmental, self-development, group, collective, informational, dialogical, communicative, interactive, game, labor, creative, art technologies.

In the work of G.F Polushkina - “Assessment of meta-subject results of education in the foreign language in basic school”, it is noted that the results of meta-subject – “mastering the basic educational program of basic general education in the foreign language shows: the ability to determine learning goals

independently, activities, the ability to generalize, establish analogies, classify, establish causal relationships, build logical reasoning, draw conclusions ”.

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